

Neuroprotective Strategies for Preterm Neonates: The Role of Therapeutic Hypothermia in Managing Hypoxic-Ischemic Encephalopathy

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Background

Early therapeutic hypothermia (TH) is the standard treatment for hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) in term neonates, reducing mortality and neurodevelopmental impairments. However, in preterm infants, its safety and efficacy remain uncertain. TH may pose risks of worsening brain injuries, emphasizing the need for targeted strategies and further research for this vulnerable population.

Introduction

- Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) significantly affects preterm neonates, with an incidence of 1-3 per 1,000 live births¹.
- Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) plays a vital role in minimizing metabolic injury in term infants and is now the standard protocol in NICU settings across the United States. It can be achieved through selective head cooling (SHC) or whole-body cooling (WBC)².
- Much is known about the neuroprotective strategies using TH in term infants, but research is limited regarding their application in preterm infants.

Aims: This study evaluates the effectiveness of TH in treating HIE in preterm infants, focusing on immediate brain insult and complications associated with TH in this vulnerable group

Figure 1. Hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE) begins with ATP depletion and primary energy failure. The latent phase permits recovery with hypothermic therapy, while the irreversible secondary phase results in neuronal damage and cell death. Image credit; Dr Putri Caesa, Created in BioRender. Putri, C. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/b21h089>

Methodology

- A search was conducted from January 5 to January 14 2025 in PubMed, Scopus, and the Cochrane Library from January 2020 to January 2025 using the search terms: neuroprotective, therapeutic hypothermia, premature, and hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy.
- Records focusing exclusively on term infants, studies solely investigating drugs or other neuroprotective agents without therapeutic hypothermia, animal studies, studies involving chromosomal abnormalities, and non-peer-reviewed articles were excluded.

Results

- A total of 10 studies focus on preterm infants, with 6 studies specifically targeting preterm infants <35 weeks gestational age.

Types of Infants Studied	Studies
Preterm (33-35 weeks)	Laddeman et al., Shipley et al., Herrera et al., Kim et al., Faix et al., and Roca-LLabrés et al.
Term and Late Preterm (35+ weeks)	Sakr et al., Babbo et al., Okulu et al., Kumar et al., Moran et al.

- Only 3 studies support the use of TH in preterm infants: Kim et al., Laddeman et al., and Moran et al.. However, these studies are limited by small sample sizes, and the results remain insignificant.
- Six studies on TH in preterm infants show limited or inconclusive support for its use, with some reporting no significant improvements in mortality or outcomes, while others highlight potential risks like increased mortality (e.g., Faix et al., Roca-LLabrés et al.).
- The study by Babbo et al. found TH increased mortality from 31% to 42% in low-income countries, such as India, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, likely due to limited medical resources, challenges in managing complications, and inadequate post-cooling care, highlighting the need for caution in resource-limited settings.

Outcome	Summary
Mortality	Therapeutic hypothermia does not reduce the primary outcome of death in infants born at 33-35 weeks. Faix et al. and Roca-LLabrés et al. found higher mortality rates in preterm infants (47.1% in Roca-LLabrés et al.). Kumar et al. also showed that preterm children undergoing TH required more inotropic support.
Intracranial Hemorrhage (ICH)	Limited specific data; MRI injury-free rates were similar between preterm and term infants, suggesting no increased risk of severe ICH.
Coagulopathy and Thrombocytopenia	Some studies (e.g., Roca-LLabrés et al.) reported coagulopathy, but it was not a consistent concern across all studies. Herrera et al. reported a 50% incidence of coagulopathy and 20% of thrombocytopenia.
Neurodevelopmental Delay (NDI)	Long-term NDI data were scarce, but Laddeman et al. reported no major developmental disabilities in preterm infants, which is promising for TH. Kumar et al. also showed a 38.9% incidence of severe NDI. Faix et al. also reported a higher incidence of moderate to severe NDI in cooled preterm infants (41%, 41%, and 24%).

Discussion

- Concerns About Hypothermia:** Cooling is not standard for preterm infants with HIE due to potential harm to hemodynamic stability and worsening brain injury³.
- Preterm Infant Susceptibilities:** Preterm infants are at risk for hyperglycemia, hypoglycemia, thrombocytopenia, clotting issues, and hemorrhage, complicating management⁴.
- Outcomes by Injury Pattern:** Injury was more prevalent in preterm (80.6%) vs. term infants (59.4%) (P = .07), with white matter injury significantly higher in preterms (66.7% vs. 25.0%, P = .001)³.
- Adjuvant Therapy for Effectiveness:** To improve outcomes, adjuvant therapies (e.g., neuroprotective agents or pharmacological treatments) alongside hypothermia could potentially enhance treatment efficacy, but more research is needed to determine their benefit in preterm infants with HIE⁵⁻⁷.

- Concerns & Limitations:** Limited evidence for TH in preterm infants, with only three studies (Kim et al., Laddeman et al., Moran et al) supporting its use, all constrained by small sample sizes. The lack of a control group, unclear baseline health differences, higher adverse events and mortality, and no long-term follow-up further limit conclusions.

Figure 2. Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) in preterm infants disrupts blood flow, weakening the blood-brain barrier and causing vascular leakage. TH also induces thrombocytopenia, increasing hemorrhage risk, and impairs oligodendrocytes, leading to periventricular leukomalacia (PVL). Systemic effects include cardiac arrhythmia, hyperglycemia, and metabolic acidosis. Image credit; Dr Putri C, Created in BioRender. Putri, C. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/r02t667>

Conclusion

- Effectiveness in Term/Late Preterm Infants:** TH is effective for term and late preterm infants (34-36 weeks) with moderate-to-severe HIE; however, evidence for late preterm outcomes is limited.
- Limited Evidence for <34 Weeks:** TH for infants <34 weeks is inconclusive due to feasibility concerns and higher complication risks.
- Socioeconomic Impact:** Outcomes vary by geography; TH is linked to higher mortality in low-income countries due to resource limitations.
- Need for Standardized Guidelines:** Further research is needed to define the safety, efficacy, and long-term outcomes of TH in preterm infants, especially those <34 weeks, for equitable clinical practices..

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